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Description of Harlomillsiidae Yu and Zhang **fam. n.** (Collembola, Entomobryomorpha)^a

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Harlomillsiidae Yu and Zhang **fam. n.**

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:D112B4E1-80A8-4826-8EAC-121F5A86E6E6>

Type genus. *Harlomillsia* Bonet, 1944

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Description. — Small-sized (0.4–0.7 mm) entomobryomorphs with a stocky body and short appendages. Ground colour light to dark grey, with evenly scattered bluish to brownish pigment dots (Fig. a). Scales present. Chaetae of various types, from smooth to strongly ciliated. Macrochaetae present on head (Fig. b), body, legs, and furca. Bothriotracha absent. Antenna four-segmented, not annulated. Ant. IV and Ant. III apically with curved spatulate chaetae (Fig. c). Prelabral chaetae 4, labral chaetae 16, all smooth and pointed, arranged as 4/2, 5, 5, 4 (Fig. d). Postantennal organs (PAO) large, with multiple asymmetric lobes (Fig. e). Eyes 4 + 4. Tibiotarsus with 7 rows of chaetae, without spatulate chaeta. Tenaculum quadridentate. Dental spines compound, with denticles or multifurcate, without sockets, arranged in inner row on basal subsegment and in inner and outer rows on distal subsegment. All dental spines fused to cuticle of dens, without sockets (Fig. f). Mucro elongated and basally twisted, with multiple dorsal teeth and two basal chaetae (Fig. g).

Etymology. — The familial name is derived from the name of the type genus *Harlomillsia*, which was named after Harlow Mills, the discoverer of the single known species *Harlomillsia oculata* (Mills, 1937).

Distribution and ecology. — The current known distribution range of the family's single species *H. oculata* includes: Asia: China (Xishuangbanna, Yunnan Province, this study); Japan (Yosii 1965); Thailand (Deharveng et al. 1986); Singapore (Murphy 1973); Indonesia (Sulawesi, Deharveng 1987). North America: the USA (Florida,

Georgia, Hawaii, Maryland, North Carolina, South Carolina, Oregon, Tennessee, Christiansen and Bellinger 1998); Mexico (Bonet 1943); Cuba (Mari-Mutt and Bellinger 1996). South America: Peru (Winter 1963). Therefore, apart from a few records from Japan and the northern states of the USA, the species is mainly distributed in the tropics of southeast Asia and central America. *H. oculata* is a typical hemiedaphic species inhabiting moss, litter, humus, and upper soil layers.

Remarks. — The genus *Harlomillsia* was originally assigned to Oncopoduridae because of its apparent similarity with *Oncopodura* in characters such as the minute body size, the presence of scales, and the structure of the furca. However, it was also noted that the genus differs strikingly from other oncopodurids in several peculiar characters, including the presence of eyes, the shape of the PAO, the form of antennal chaetae, and the absence of tibiotarsal clavate chaetae (Mills 1937). In addition, Szeptycki (1977) further revealed substantial differences between *Harlomillsia* and *Oncopodura* in body chaetotaxy. Our detailed morphological examination revealed more differences between *Harlomillsia* and *Oncopodura* in labral and cephalic chaetotaxy, which is even more similar to Tomoceridae. Notably, among all Collembola, the presence of additional labral chaetae is so far only known from *Harlomillsia* and the tomocerid subfamily Lepidophorellinae Absolon, 1903. Our phylogenomic analyses using best-fitting approaches have also demonstrated that the previously defined Oncopoduridae is paraphyletic, supporting the separation of *Harlomillsia* from Oncopoduridae.

Figure. Morphological characters of Harlomillsiidae **fam. n.** Yu and Zhang (a–g), and *Novacerus tasmanicus* (h, i). a) descaled specimen in alcohol; b) dorsal cephalic chaetotaxy, arrows point to sockets of macrochaetae except for those around antennal bases; c) antennal segment (Ant.) IV and distal part of Ant. III, stack of 11 photos, asterisks mark the curved spatulate chaetae; d) labral chaetotaxy, stack of 9 photos, asterisks mark the bases of labral chaetae; e) postantennal organ (PAO); f) dental spines, stack of 12 photos, asterisks mark the bases of spines; g) mucro, stack of 4

photos; h) labral chaetotaxy; i) PAO.

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